

Authentic assessment activities for oral Malay language skills in primary schools

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ABSTRACT

The quality of assessment conducted by teachers plays an important role in ensuring students' mastery of Malay language skills, particularly oral skills. Assessment through direct activities can highlight students' true potential and skills. Therefore, this study aims to explore the forms of authentic assessment activities for Malay language oral skills in primary schools in Malaysia. The study design is qualitative, using a case study method involving one case across multiple locations. This study involves five Malay language teachers as study participants from five primary schools located in five different states in Malaysia. The research methods used include interviews, observations, and document analysis. The study findings were analyzed thematically using Nvivo14 software. The results of the study identified seven forms of authentic assessment activities implemented by Malay language teachers: role-playing, storytelling, stimulus materials, questioning, edutainment, presentations, and language games. Interview interpretations are supported by observation and document analysis results, which prove that teachers conduct various forms of authentic assessment activities as the best alternative assessments for evaluating primary school students' Malay language oral skills. Authentic assessment focuses on engaging and realistic activities to facilitate teachers in directly observing students' language development and skills.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Oral skills refer to an individual's ability to listen, understand, and communicate effectively through speaking. These skills involve several key components, including the ability to listen attentively, comprehend conveyed messages, articulate thoughts clearly, and respond appropriately and accurately to questions or conversations [1]. Indeed, there is a need to enhance oral skills in schools because these skills are essential as a tool for learning and acquiring other skills in education [2]. Oral skills are productive communication skills between individuals using language [3]. So, oral skills are language skills that all students need to master [1]. In schools, oral skills can be observed not only from the teaching perspective but also from the assessment conducted by teachers in the classroom. In line with the national education transformation, continuous assessment has replaced test-based evaluation. Previously, assessment and evaluation in schools focused more on grading and students' excellence in examinations rather than the comprehensive mastery of learning objectives. The interim strategic plan 2011-2020 and the Malaysian education development plan 2013-2025 also emphasize that this transition in the assessment system aims to make it more flexible and holistic for student development [4].

Classroom assessment has offered a more comprehensive evaluation to observe student development. In classroom assessment, various alternative assessment methods are recommended to replace pencil-and-paper tests, including authentic assessment. Authentic assessment is task-based assessment conducted by students during teaching and learning sessions in the classroom. Authentic assessment enables the application of theoretical components to real life situations [5], [6]. It involves practical or “hands-on” tasks that require students to apply various skills to complete the tasks. Authentic assessment gathers information about students' development, progress, abilities, and performance and provides feedback on the quality of teaching by the teacher. This assessment is fully conducted by teachers, who are responsible for identifying each student's abilities, mastery, progress, and achievements, particularly in mastering oral skills.

This study aimed to address issues related to the implementation of authentic assessment of Malay language oral skills in primary schools in Malaysia. According to Welsh and Elliott [7], an excellent education system is evaluated based on student learning success and development throughout the learning process. The Malaysian Ministry of Education aspires to enhance the quality of education so that the national education system is among the top one-third in the world. However, achieving this goal is not easy because the quality of teaching, including assessment implementation, is a key element in determining student achievement and the success of the national education system.

Oral skills are considered secondary and less important to be learned directly compared to reading and writing skills, causing teachers to neglect the teaching of oral skills in the classroom. However, in Colognesi *et al.* report [8], it is stated that mastering oral skills is easier compared to writing skills. Teachers face difficulties in preparing listening and speaking activities for teaching oral skills. Additionally, linear and one-way teaching also makes it difficult for teachers to provide systematic, effective, and engaging listening and speaking activities. This situation leads to the mastery level of oral skills often being questioned and rarely assessed by teachers in the classroom. In fact, the study by Adie *et al.* [9] mentioned that critical changes are needed in the assessment culture at schools to maintain good performance.

Classroom assessment, which replaced the primary school achievement test, provides students with opportunities to gain experience and skills in the subjects studied. However, teachers face difficulties in administering oral skill assessments compared to other language skills. Some teachers are less aware of conducting assessment activities appropriate to the students' levels. Furthermore, classroom assessment practices are said to still be outdated [10]. Sukma *et al.* [11] also stated that the assessment process for oral skills has not yet reached optimal implementation by teachers. This was also reported by Putri *et al.* [12], which found that three factors hindering the full implementation of authentic assessment are the amount of time, the number of students, and the teaching aids. Therefore, teachers are encouraged to diversify assessment forms to evaluate student development more accurately. In conclusion, this study is conducted to explore the authentic assessment of Malay language oral skills in primary schools by examining more effective forms of authentic assessment activities. The reality is that this is aimed at making authentic assessment an alternative assessment preferred by teachers to evaluate students' language skills, thereby improving the quality of teaching and enhancing student learning outcomes in Malay language oral skills.

This study was conducted to explore the forms of activities for authentic assessment of oral Malay language skills in primary schools. Through the findings of this study, by the end of the research, we can identify several authentic activities that can be implemented to assess the oral Malay language skills of primary school students. Therefore, this study was specifically conducted to achieve one research objective, which is to explore the forms of authentic assessment activities for Malay language oral skills in primary schools.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research related to assessment and evaluation has been widely conducted by previous researchers. However, studies on authentic assessment are still limited in Malaysia, especially in the field of Malay language, particularly for oral skills. Authentic assessment is an alternative assessment used to interpret student learning in the classroom. Several studies [13], [14] reported that authentic assessment is the best type of assessment to be applied in evaluating students' language skills performance. They also added that authentic assessment can evaluate the entire learning process, not just test students' knowledge at the end of the teaching and learning process. Mohamed and Lebar [15] also produced a literature review article showing that authentic assessment has good potential in measuring higher-order thinking skills among students.

Several studies have been conducted to examine and develop authentic assessment, such as the study by Sekarsari *et al.* [16], which developed an authentic assessment model for speaking skills. This model outlines six activities, including role-playing, information gaps, picture talks, short Q&A sessions, story sequences, and paired dialogues for authentic speaking skills assessment. Similar findings were reported by Zaim *et al.* [17], as well as Ulhasanah *et al.* [18], which showed the use of various types of authentic assessments such as short Q&A sessions, paired dialogues, oral reports, and storytelling.

Additionally, other studies, such as those by Inayah *et al.* [19], have listed activities such as teacher observation, interviews, short Q&A sessions, and storytelling sequences to assess speaking skills. Purnawarman and Darajati [20] also mentioned activities such as video screenings, demonstrations, attitude assessments, and interviews as effective authentic assessment activities. Moreover, the study by Rahmawati [21] stated that teachers use observation during the teaching and learning process, written assessments, performance assessments, peer assessments, and open interviews to assess Indonesian language speaking skills.

However, several studies have reported problems faced by teachers in implementing authentic assessment. For instance, the study by Rahmawati [21] found that the implementation of authentic assessment in language learning does not follow the lesson plan but is only adapted to the classroom conditions. Sekarsari *et al.* [16] also reported that authentic assessment for speaking skills does not fully meet the needs and knowledge levels of students. This issue is also seen in the lack of implementation references, such as the study by Aziz *et al.* [22], which reported challenges due to the absence of clear guidelines for implementing authentic English language assessment. Similar findings were reported by Zaim *et al.* [23], who mentioned communication problems, assessment forms, and assessment topics as major obstacles for teachers in implementing authentic oral skills assessment.

Based on previous studies, it is found that research related to assessment and evaluation has been widely conducted by previous researchers, especially in the aspects of teachers' knowledge and practices. However, the implementation of authentic assessment forms for Malay language oral skills in primary schools in Malaysia has not yet been conducted. Therefore, this study needs to be conducted to help teachers identify more effective and efficient authentic assessment activities.

3. METHOD

This study was conducted using a qualitative approach and selected a case study method involving one case across multiple locations. In line with the selection of this qualitative case study design, the researcher used interviews as the primary method, while observation and document analysis served as supporting methods for data collection. The study locations included five selected primary schools from five states in Malaysia, namely Sarawak, Perak, Kelantan, Melaka, and Selangor. Each state represents a zone in Malaysia. This qualitative case study used purposive sampling and selected five Malay language teachers from five schools as the study participants. The study participants are Malay language teachers who are actively involved in authentic assessment. The instruments used in this study were interview protocols, observation checklists, and document analysis checklists. All data obtained using these three instruments were analyzed using the Nvivo14 software. The data analysis process was conducted by examining the data in detail to identify categories, themes, and sub-themes that describe the actual phenomena of this study.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Background of study participants

The study participants involved in this research comprised ten individuals selected through purposive sampling [24] to obtain information about the research phenomenon. The study participants were selected based on predetermined criteria to meet the needs of the research. The participants were Malay language teachers who teach in five selected primary schools. The background of the study participants is as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 shows the profile of the five study participants involved in this research. The participants consist of four female teachers and one male teacher, aged between 38 and 53 years. All participants have a Bachelor's degree, and one participant holds a Master's degree as their highest academic qualification. All participants are Malay language option teachers. Additionally, all participants have more than 10 years of teaching experience and more than five years of experience teaching Malay language. This diverse background of the participants enriches the information to be more detailed in achieving the research objectives.

Table 1. Background of study participants

Participants	State	School	Gender	Age (years)	Academic qualifications	Major	Teaching experience (Years)
GBM1	Sarawak	SR1	L	53	Bachelor's degree	Malay language	30
GBM2	Perak	SR2	P	38	Bachelor's degree	Malay language	13
GBM3	Kelantan	SR3	P	44	Bachelor's degree	Malay language	23
GBM4	Melaka	SR4	P	51	Master's degree	Malay language	23
GBM5	Selangor	SR5	P	42	Bachelor's degree	Malay language	15

4.2. Forms of authentic assessment activities

In implementing oral skills assessment, several types of activities can be conducted to ensure the assessment objectives are achieved through direct and realistic activities. These activity-based assessments can directly involve students and evaluate their mastery, particularly in oral skills, in a realistic and holistic manner. The data collected through the three data collection methods were analyzed and identified seven forms of authentic assessment activities for oral skills conducted by Malay language teachers, as shown in Table 2. Each form of authentic assessment activity is detailed more clearly.

Table 2. List of categories, themes, and subthemes

Category	Theme	Subtheme
Forms of authentic assessment activities	a. Role-playing	- Spontaneous role-playing - Planned role-playing
	b. Storytelling	- Spontaneous storytelling - Planned storytelling - Retelling a story
	c. Stimulus materials	- Use of various types of materials - Speaking about pictures
	d. Question and Answer	- Open-ended questions - Theme-based questions
	e. Edutainment	- Singing - Poetry recitation
	f. Presentation	- Discuss and present
	g. Language games	- Group-based games - Movement-based games - Competition-based games

4.2.1. Role-playing

Role-playing, or in other words, simulation, is an activity where students take on a role to enact. This practical activity is conducted directly by students during teaching and learning sessions. This activity can be divided into two types: spontaneous role-playing and planned role-playing. Both of these sub-themes are explained and detailed individually to better illustrate the research findings.

a. Spontaneous role-playing

Spontaneous role-playing refers to acting performed spontaneously, driven by one's own emotions and without coercion. Participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM3, and GBM4 stated that spontaneous role-playing activities involve assigning students a situation or character to enact spontaneously in front of the class. Additionally, participants noted that spontaneous role-playing can also be conducted as a game, where students act out a character and others guess the role being portrayed.

“Usually, I give students a dialogue text to enact, or I give them a situation to act out spontaneously. For example, if we give them a proverb card, students are asked to enact the meaning of that proverb. Sometimes, we can ask them to do a gesture and have their peers guess what they are acting out.” (TB/GBM3:315-321)

This aspect is clearly supported by observations made by the researcher at the study location.

Observation note: GBM1 screened a video in front of the class for student viewing. Students engaged in a Q&A session about the video. Students were then asked to reenact the character they watched in the video. Students mimicked and reenacted the dialogue spoken by the character. (P3/SR1/GBM1)

Excerpts from interviews and observation notes for this finding are also supported by document analysis. Through these observation notes, document analysis for each lesson plan related to teaching and learning sessions indeed records spontaneous role-playing activities conducted. For example, AD/RPH9/GBM2 records “*Students simulating using an oven*” during the induction activity, serving as supporting evidence for this finding.

b. Planned role-playing

Typically, planned role-playing activities are known to students in advance before they are conducted. According to participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM4, and GBM5, for these planned role-playing activities, careful planning is necessary including preparation of materials, characters, scenes, and informing students beforehand.

Additionally, students may be given a script to memorize for initial preparation before the actual role-playing session takes place. This finding is supported by excerpts from participant interviews, such as:

“For example, for the role-playing activity earlier, I might need to prepare materials like puppets, masks, and I immediately assign roles and the students involved. These students are the ones I assess. Once I know which students are involved, I inform them early so they can prepare.” (TB/GBM2:345-348)

Through observations documented in P5/SR1/GBM1 and P10/SR2/GBM2, participants were found to have implemented planned role-playing activities using a variety of teaching aids, and prior activity information was provided to the students.

Observation note: *GBM2 dressed as a warrior, provided replica swords, word cards, and dialogue texts to perform the Hang Tuah and Hang Jebat role-playing activity. Two selected students portraying the warrior's roles also wore warrior-like costumes.* (P10/SR2/GBM2)

This data triangulation is evident through the lesson plan writing of participants, for instance, AD/RPH5/GBM2 which records the “*Hang Tuah and Hang Jebat*” role-playing activity that was indeed pre-planned by the participant. The lesson plan notes also confirm GBM2's preparation of dialogue scripts beforehand.

4.2.2. Storytelling

Storytelling is an activity of narrating a story to others. Storytelling also serves as an authentic oral activity that can be implemented to encourage students to speak and interact orally. Based on the research findings, there are several types of storytelling activities that can be conducted by the study participants during teaching and learning sessions.

a. Spontaneous storytelling

According to participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM3, GBM4, and GBM5 during interviews, spontaneous storytelling is usually associated with stories about students' existing knowledge, their experiences, and things around them. Additionally, participants noted that spontaneous storytelling requires students to tell stories using their own words, thereby facilitating teachers in assessing the oral skills mastered by the students. The following excerpt from participant interviews clearly illustrates this finding:

“When it comes to storytelling, I like spontaneous activities. I like students to tell stories using their own words. They tell stories based on what they've read, their experiences, stories about events around them.” (TB/GBM4:393-395)

Based on the observations made, study participants ask students to tell stories about their experiences and existing knowledge of something. The following observation note provides a clear picture of this finding:

Observation note: *GBM3 showed a picture of a cityscape. GBM3 asked students to narrate their experience of traveling to the capital city.* (P28/SR3/GBM3)

Furthermore, this finding is supported by notes in the document AD/RPH18/GBM3, which records “*Students narrating their experience of traveling to the capital city.*” Notes in the lesson plan document confirm that spontaneous storytelling activities were conducted during the teaching and learning sessions, thereby serving as authentic assessments of oral proficiency.

b. Planned storytelling

Planned storytelling focuses on storytelling activities using pre-prepared story texts. According to participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM3, GBM4, and GBM5, for this planned storytelling activity, students are provided with a story text to memorize before being asked to narrate it in front of the class. Additionally, incomplete story texts can be provided to students, requiring them to complete the story before narrating it in front of the class.

“I usually prepare the story text, a simple one, not too long, and ask the students to memorize or read the story at home. The next day, the students will narrate the story in front of the class.” (TB/GBM2:388-390)

This research finding is supported by observational notes conducted on GBM3 participants (P28/SR3/GBM3), who engaged in group activities to create a story based on provided pictures and cue cards.

Observation note: *Through group discussions, students created a story based on provided pictures and cue cards. Each group collaborated to produce a story and narrated it in front of the class.* (P28/SR3/GBM3)

This is further evidenced by the lesson plan written by GBM3 (AD/RPH18/GBM3), which states “*Students will discuss and share ideas to create a story based on provided pictures and cue cards*” in the activity section.

c. Retelling a story

Retelling a story that has been read, heard, or watched is an activity that can be conducted during storytelling sessions. Study participants GBM2, GBM4, and GBM5 indicated that students retell stories using their own words. This finding can be illustrated by the following excerpt from participant interviews:

“If I want students to retell a story they heard, I’ll first show the story using an LCD in front of the class... Then, we can ask the students to retell the story using their own words.” (TB/GBM2:338-343)

Observations on GBM5 participants revealed that students were asked to retell the steps of making ‘kuih tepung pelita’ (a traditional Malaysian dessert) that had been narrated by another student in front of the class, as noted:

Observation note: *Students were asked to retell the steps of making ‘kuih tepung pelita’ that had been narrated by their peers in front of the class using their own words.* (P25/SR5/GBM5)

This practice is also clearly documented by GBM5 in their lesson plan (AD/RPH15/GBM9), which indicates that retelling activities were conducted in “One-two-group” format, initially individually, then in pairs and groups.

4.2.3. Stimulus materials

The next type of activity is one that is guided by stimulus materials. This activity is conducted orally using prepared materials, either as primary or supporting materials during teaching and learning sessions. Research findings identified several aspects mentioned by participants regarding the use of stimulus materials, each elaborated in detail.

a. Use of various types of materials

Stimulus materials used in teaching and learning can consist of various forms such as existing materials, printed materials, electronic materials, and others. The use of stimulus materials indeed stimulates students' interest and knowledge regarding the subject matter conveyed. Participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM3, GBM4, and GBM5 stated that easily accessible stimulus materials, physical materials, graphic materials, and others are used to stimulate students' thinking related to the theme and content of the lesson.

“Any materials like physical materials, graphic materials like pictures, audio, video. These materials I will use to stimulate students' thinking about the theme on that day.” (TB/GBM5:452-455)

This is also evident from the stimulus materials used by participants during these activities. Observation note P9/SR2/GBM2 clearly illustrates this research finding:

Observation note: *GBM2 dressed as a warrior. GBM2 used teaching aids such as replica keris, word cards, pictures, and dialogue texts.* (P9/SR2/GBM2)

Data triangulation can be seen in the analysis of documents prepared. Analysis of all lesson plans provided by participants includes notes on teaching aids for each teaching session conducted. These materials consist of various types, as noted in document AD/RPH13/GBM4, listing teaching aids used by participants such as videos, dialogue texts, pictures, and A4 papers.

b. Speaking about pictures

Authentic activities based on stimulus materials can also be conducted in the form of a picture talk activity. According to participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM3, GBM4, and GBM5, the activity of speaking about pictures can be conducted using images from various sources related to the theme and content of the lesson. Participants added that through these pictures, students can express opinions, ideas, or even narrate about the given images.

“Pictures related to the theme. But we can vary the pictures, for example, pictures in the form of puzzles, pictures in magazines, newspapers. So, these materials we can bring to school for students to find pictures and explain about them.” (TB/GBM1:359-362)

This finding is supported by observations and document analysis conducted by the researcher. Observation findings from P16/SR3/GBM3 found that GBM3 used newspaper clippings during a teaching and learning session.

Observation note: GBM3 showed pictures from newspaper clippings to the students. GBM3 and students discussed the pictures, and selected students were asked to give their views on the pictures. (P16/SR3/GBM3)

Observations during the teaching and learning sessions were indeed recorded in the lesson plans prepared by the study participants. Document AD/RPH10/GBM3 indicates the note *“Students speak about pictures”* in the activity section of the lesson plan. Therefore, this data triangulation indicates that the activity of speaking about pictures is an authentic activity conducted to effectively assess students' oral skills.

4.2.4. Question and answer

Another form of authentic oral skill activity is the question and answer session. In the usual teaching and learning sessions, the question and answer activity is frequently conducted, whether directly or indirectly. The study's findings indicate that the participants indeed provided statements regarding the implementation of questioning activities by considering several aspects.

a. Open-ended questions

The activity of asking open-ended questions aims to elicit ideas, opinions, and views from students regarding the lesson content being presented. According to participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM3, and GBM4, open-ended questions can be posed to students during the induction phase, during activity execution, or at the end of the PdP session. These open-ended questions encourage students to voice their opinions and views. This can be evidenced by the following excerpt from participant interviews:

“Then the questions I ask can stimulate students to give ideas. So, it's not closed questions, it's open-ended questions. When it's open-ended, it's more about ideas blossoming.” (TB/GBM1:609-611)

Observation notes have found that all PdP sessions conducted by the participants included question and answer activities, both directly and indirectly, posed to the students.

Observation note: GBM5 asked students to express their opinions and views on the preservation of songket heritage. Students raised their hands to express their opinions. (P26/SR5/GBM5)

Furthermore, document analysis clearly shows notes made by participant GBM5 in document AD/RPH16/GBM10, detailing open-ended questions posed to students during the PdP activities. The note in the document reads, *“Follow-up Question: Why do we need to preserve the cultural heritage of songket fabric?”*

b. Theme-based questions

The question and answer activity regarding learning themes was also highlighted by participants GBM2, GBM3, GBM4, and GBM5 during their interview sessions. According to the participants, questions about the theme should be posed to students to stimulate their interest in the issues and learning themes being discussed.

“... maybe we can discuss with the students, or ask them questions about the theme we are going to learn that day. For example, a theme on safety, ‘Why is it important for us to ensure our own safety?’ so students will give their opinions.” (TB/GBM2:421-424)

Observations made on participant GBM3 (P16/SR3/GBM3) showed a question and answer session with students regarding the use of mobile phones, linking it to the Safety learning theme.

Observation note: *GBM3 conducted a question and answer session with students about the PdP theme. GBM3 connected the theme to students' daily lives in the safe use of mobile phones. (P16/SR3/GBM3)*

This triangulation of data is supported by document analysis conducted on document AD/RPH10/GBM3, which recorded “*Teacher questioning students about the use of mobile phones*” under the induction activity notes.

4.2.5. Edutainment

Edutainment activities emphasize a fun and planned learning environment. These activities are conducted through relaxed, engaging, entertaining, and meaningful learning experiences to reinforce students' understanding and foster their interest in participating in the teaching and learning sessions. In implementing edutainment activities, the study's findings revealed that the participants mentioned several types of authentic activities that encompass edutainment.

a. Singing

Singing is an authentic and enjoyable activity. According to participants GBM1 and GBM2, singing activities can be implemented as oral activities that boost students' enthusiasm for learning. Moreover, students' interest in singing activities is also considered to ensure they enjoy participating in the teaching and learning sessions. This can be evidenced by the following excerpt from participant interviews:

“My class students love singing. So, I always incorporate singing into my teaching sessions. At the very least, I can invite students to sing before concluding the teaching session.” (TB/GBM1:420-422)

Observational findings revealed several teaching and learning sessions conducted by participants GBM1 (P3/SR1/GBM1) and GBM5 (P29/SR5/GBM5) included singing activities. GBM1 conducted singing activities as part of the induction activity, while GBM5 organized singing activities before concluding the teaching session.

Observation note: *Students sang the song “Sayang Semuanya” accompanied by music. GBM1 linked the song to the learning theme of the day. (P3/SR1/GBM1)*

Singing activities are comprehensively documented in the Lower Primary Malay Language Curriculum and Assessment Document (DSKP *Bahasa Melayu Sekolah Rendah*) under the “Language Arts” section. Singing is one of the elements included in this section and is incorporated into content standards and learning standards that students are expected to master. For example, document AD/DSKPBM/T3 records the learning standard “*Singing songs according to the rhythm of children's songs and folk songs and explaining the beautiful language meanings in song lyrics.*”

b. Poetry recitation

Next, poetry recitation activities encompassing verses, poems, rhymes, and the like are also categorized as edutainment activities. According to study participants during interview sessions TB/GBM1:288-290 and TB/GBM5:199-201, activities such as declaiming poems, reciting verses, and composing pantun (traditional Malay quatrain) are considered edutainment activities that can serve as authentic oral skill exercises.

“We can see, if a student excels in language arts orally, they can compose poems, recite verses with interesting intonation, tell stories effectively, and speak confidently.” (TB/GBM5:199-201)

Observations from P15/SR3/GBM3 and P21/SR4/GBM4 sessions indicate that study participants conducted poetry recitation activities such as composing pantun and reciting verses.

Observation note: *Each group recited verses accompanied by kompang (traditional Malay hand drum). Each group presented their performance in front of the class. (P21/SR4/GBM4)*

Analysis of documents confirms that poetry recitation activities are indeed documented in the lower primary Malay language curriculum and assessment document (DSKP *Bahasa Melayu Sekolah Rendah*) from Year 1 to Year 6. For instance, document AD/DSKPBM/T1 notes “*Reciting pantun with proper intonation;*” under the language arts aspect learning standard clearly indicates that poetry recitation is recommended as an activity in the language learning process. Furthermore, document analysis also found in document AD/RPH12/GBM8 that poetry recitation activities were recorded in the activity section and noted “*Reciting and performing verses with suitable rhythm and expressing the overall ideas of the verse*” as a learning standard in the teaching plan.

4.2.6. Presentation

Presentation refers to the activity of explaining, describing, and displaying something to others. Therefore, in this context, presentation is an activity where students present their work in front of teachers and other students. This activity requires students to interact orally while presenting their work.

a. Discuss and present

The activity of discussion and presentation is usually conducted together to ensure that the work presented has undergone a discussion process, especially within specific groups. According to study participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM3, and GBM5, during discussion and presentation activities, students are evaluated based on their interaction during group discussions, as well as their presentation style and the quality of the work presented.

“For example, in presentation tasks, we assess students during their group discussions, interaction with group mates and teachers, and then we assess during their presentation, their delivery style, intonation, pronunciation, and so on. The outcome is what the students present. That's their work.” (TB/GBM4:164-167)

Through observations, it was found that study participants indeed conducted these discussion and presentation activities as part of their teaching and learning practices. Observational findings indicate that all discussion and presentation activities were conducted in groups to observe interactions within those groups. The following observation note provides a clear picture of these findings.

Observation note: Each group conducted a presentation to present their group work. The discussion and presentation session showed students interacting to complete their tasks. (P13/SR2/GBM2)

These observation notes align with document analysis conducted on various lesson plans prepared by the study participants. For example, teaching plan documents indicate records of discussion and presentation activities conducted, such as the note “*Each group presents the i-Think map they have produced*” in document AD/RPH17/GBM3. This activity can encourage students to communicate with their peers and teachers, thereby enhancing their oral skills.

4.2.7. Language games

Playing is a natural part of childhood. Therefore, the concept of learning through play is an approach that brings students closer to knowledge through games. Typically, students interact extensively during gameplay. Therefore, this aligns with research findings indicating that language game activities can serve as authentic assessments of oral skills.

a. Group-based games

Games conducted in group settings are generally more enjoyable than individual games. This was also noted by study participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM3, and GBM4, who expressed that language games in group formats have a greater impact on students' oral learning. Participants opined that student enjoy playing in groups because they can interact with each other to solve the game.

“I usually do crossword puzzles, quizzes, riddles, hotseat, musical chairs. Usually, these games are done in groups, where students discuss together to solve the quiz.” (TB/GBM2:397-398)

This finding is further supported by observations and document analysis. Observation P23/SR4/GBM4 shows that study participants conducted the language game “Future Snake and Ladder” in groups during a teaching session.

Observation note: *Students played the language game “Future Snake and Ladder” in groups. Each group representative rolled the dice and moved the marker on the slide displayed in front of the class. Each square in the game board had instructions that students had to follow. Each group member worked together to solve the problems presented on the respective squares.* (P23/SR4/GBM4)

Additionally, this finding is clearly evidenced through document analysis of AD/RPH14/GBM4, which noted “*Learning Style: Kinesthetic - Language Games.*”

b. Movement-based games

Through the data analysis conducted, games involving movement were also mentioned by the study participants. According to study participants GBM1, GBM2, GBM4, and GBM5, games involving movement typically require a relatively spacious area, thus outdoor locations for teaching and learning sessions can be considered.

“For example, I’ve integrated Physical Education into teaching Malay language through activities like games, down there... at the assembly area, so students engage in kinesthetic movements....” (TB/GBM2:82-84)

Through observations made in P11/SR2/GBM2 and P29/SR5/GBM5, it was found that study participants conducted language games involving movement during teaching sessions.

Observation note: *Each group moved to each station to complete the information provided by each station's attendant. Group members listened attentively to the information conveyed by the station attendants to complete the related tasks.* (P29/SR5/GBM5)

Data triangulation is also evident in the document analysis of AD/RPH19/GBM9, which notes “*Students were divided into several groups for the ‘Farm Station’ game.*” This note demonstrates that station-based games requiring students to move from one station to another can be implemented as authentic assessments of oral skills.

c. Competition-based games

In essence, humans naturally enjoy the thrill of competition. Therefore, language games in the form of competitions can also be conducted to cater to this human inclination, especially among children. According to GBM2, GBM3, GBM4, GBM5, language learning through game competitions becomes more enjoyable. This approach can effectively engage students to actively participate in competitions. Furthermore, to boost students' enthusiasm for participating, rewards or incentives can be provided.

“Any group that successfully completes the game earlier will receive tokens or stickers. I use a reward chart concept here.” (TB/GBM2:473-475)

Observations on GBM4 from observation P22/SR4/GBM4 indicate that GBM4 conducted an oral question-and-answer game based on images between two groups.

Observation note: *The game started with Group A posing a question answered by Group B. Group B successfully answered the question and earned points. Then, Group B posed a question to the opponent orally. Group A failed to answer the question, so Group B, who posed the question, earned points. The game continued for 15 minutes. The group with the highest accumulated points was declared the winner of the competition.* (P22/SR4/GBM4)

Document analysis indicates details of language games in competition form in the lesson plan AD/RPH13/GBM4, such as “*Groups failing to pose a question or answer the posed question are considered losing.*” Thus, it is clear that language games conducted in groups, competitions, or involving movement can be implemented to encourage students to interact and communicate while solving the games.

5. DISCUSSION

This study finds that various forms of authentic activities have been implemented in the teaching and learning process, thereby serving as authentic assessments to effectively evaluate students' oral skills. These activities include role-playing, storytelling, stimulus materials, questioning and answering, educational

entertainment, presentations, and language games, all of which play crucial roles in enhancing oral interaction and language skills among students. Role-playing activities, including spontaneous acting and planned performances, were found to be highly effective in improving students' oral skills. Spontaneous acting allows students to creatively respond to given situations, while planned performances enable better preparation through the use of teaching aids such as dialogue texts and predefined characters. This is consistent with the previous findings [25] who reported that role-playing methods enhance speaking skills and increase motivation among students to speak in English.

Additionally, storytelling activities enable students to use their imagination to orally narrate stories. Ramalingam *et al.* [26] demonstrated that such activities not only enhance fluency in oral skills but also boost students' confidence. Meanwhile, activities involving stimulus materials like pictures, videos, and existing materials are used to spark ideas and assist students in developing their narratives or discussions. The use of these materials was found to increase students' interest and active engagement in oral activities. In Umirova research report [27], it is stated that the use of authentic materials can enhance students' language skills. The research further added that using genuine and real materials can increase students' interest in learning the language. The findings of this study are also reported in several previous studies [28], [29].

Entertainment-based educational activities such as singing and poetry are indeed capable of making learning more enjoyable and interactive. The same applies to language game activities, which make teaching and learning sessions more engaging and actively involve students in their implementation. In reality, students tend to prefer enjoyable and entertaining learning experiences. Previous studies that support this finding include research by Hasibuan *et al.* [30], all of which found that entertainment-based learning, such as singing, can provide students with an enjoyable learning experience, thereby enhancing their oral skills proficiency.

Moreover, question and answer activities conducted at the beginning of teaching serve to unearth students' existing knowledge and prepare them for the topics and themes to be covered in the teaching and learning session. This activity helps students think critically and formulate relevant questions. Furthermore, presentation activities provide opportunities for students to organize and systematically deliver information in front of peers and teachers. These activities can help students improve their oral communication skills and build confidence in public speaking. Daud *et al.* research report [31] also indicates that seminar presentations can be used as an activity to improve oral skills. Moreover, presentation activities also provide students with the opportunity to engage in discussions to complete the given tasks. These oral discussion sessions can improve students' oral skills. This aligns with the findings of previous study [8], which reported that oral discussions are more effective than written discussions.

Indeed, the findings regarding these authentic activities align with previous studies [16]–[20]. These studies have outlined several authentic oral skills activities that can help enhance students' mastery of oral skills in schools. Moreover, these findings demonstrate that Malay language teachers are creative in diversifying oral skills activities for authentic assessment. This is also consistent with several previous studies [32], [33], which claimed that the application of authentic assessment in the classroom is superior to traditional assessment in evaluating oral skills.

6. CONCLUSION

Authentic assessment activities for Malay language oral skills in primary schools are crucial and relevant in enhancing the quality of assessment, especially in assessing oral proficiency. These assessments not only provide students with opportunities to apply their language knowledge in meaningful and real-world contexts but also encourage more interactive and critical learning. Authentic assessment is also relevant in its hands-on implementation and close connection to students' real-life experiences. Therefore, these activities help improve students' communication abilities, providing them with more opportunities to practice and use language in diverse and engaging situations.

With the implementation of authentic assessment in primary schools, particularly for the Malay language, assessments can be conducted more realistically, holistically, and continuously. This type of assessment is not solely focused within the classroom but can also be carried out outside the classroom. This provides teachers with the opportunity to assess students comprehensively, emphasizing all aspects of mastery and skills. Moreover, this approach addresses the shortcomings of traditional assessments, which only evaluate theoretical knowledge through pencil-and-paper tests.

Overall, authentic assessment of Malay language oral skills enriches students' learning experiences and contributes to the development of more holistic and meaningful oral skills. Furthermore, in addition to assessing oral skills, this authentic assessment can also be used to evaluate other language skills (reading and writing). Therefore, it is recommended that these assessments be expanded and optimized within the education system to ensure that students derive maximum benefits in mastering language skills, particularly Malay language.

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